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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE OR MENTAL DEBILITATION?

ABSTRACT

This essay contends that artificial intelligence is tantamount to mental debilitation because AI usurps mental operations, which are the function of the human mind. By providing ready-made answers, it hinders reasoning and thereby enfeebles the mind. In addition, generative AI narrows down searches and limits a researcher's horizon by offering a fragmented "filter bubble". Tracking requested research topics, AI reduces the range of issues provided, thereby cutting off diverse information as well as some semantic fields that could be of importance. This constitutes a philosophical problem as it restricts critical thinking. The "filter bubble" condemns the user to the gnoseological loneliness of a person locked in a circle of the same cognitive interests selected by the algorithms of social networks. The algorithms are not always helpful. Experience implanted in people's consciousness with the help of "filter bubbles" has soft-drawing consequences for the unsuspecting public, who are unknowingly being drawn into "funnels" of interests. Among the methods that will be used to drive home this point is a case study of media information regarding the demise of Queen Elizabeth II.

Keywords: artificial intelligence; "filter bubbles"; loneliness; virtual reality; critical thinking

INTRODUCTION

The death of Queen Elizabeth II of Great Britain was announced by the media on September 8, 2022. She died at the age of 96 in her lovely castle in Scotland. With a reign of over 70 years, she was the world's longest-reigning and oldest head of state.

A user interested in the life of the Queen spent several hours or days requesting relevant information and was only guaranteed a fragmented "filter bubble". Artificial intelligence, tracking the topic of request, narrowed down the

range of issues provided, thereby cutting off some information that is more pressing, large-scale, diversified, or some other important semantic field of the day, for example, the slowing down of YouTube in Russia.

This capsule of debilitated reality created by artificial intelligence has become not just a technical miscalculation or psychological inconvenience, but a philosophical problem. The “filter bubble” condemns the user to the gnoseological loneliness of a person locked in a circle of the same cognitive interests selected by the algorithms of social networks; such epic loneliness can develop into a moral and psychological one. It may develop political inadequacy and neuroses if, by accident or intentionally, the person happens to draw marked attention to wars, epidemics, catastrophes, conspiracy theories, etc. In this case, we are talking about the loss of critical thinking.

A personal example might help illustrate my point. Two years ago, I was following the news about the health of Queen Elizabeth II, who made history not only because of her long life, but also because of her personal wisdom and valour. She was not a fictional queen from the people’s favourite fantasy (which once again testifies in favour of understanding post-modernity as a New Middle Age) and not a doll on the throne; neither was she just a candidate-from-the-infantry or from-the-cavalry, who made her way to elected power for 4-8-16 or more years. Queen Elizabeth II was a strong, active ruler, appreciated by her people, and simply a most worthy woman. For several days, I chose information from the ‘web’ about her long, eventful, and great life, about her demise, this sad and at the same time majestic event, admiring not the monarchy, of course, but the monarch. As a result, for almost two years, the ‘web’ relentlessly fed me with information of only two types: this and that, as well as such and such, had died, expired, slumped, passed away, perished, died a natural or unnatural death, and about how exactly King Charles III and the poor Princess of Wales, Kate Middleton, were feeling, and also how the solemn events of the Empire, the Commonwealth, were celebrated, such as the parade in honour of the official birthday of King Charles III and the birthdays of the princes and princess, or about the men’s Wimbledon tournament.

This is, to put it in Russian, смешно и грешно (funny and unholy). The most stunning tag for me was the sociometric data about a university employee, AD Scientific Index 2024 (citation statistics: 43 for the previous year, Hirsch index 2, etc.), offered right away in August of 2024. I will withhold the name and the university, but the AD Scientific Index described was my son, who died and was buried six years ago. I can imagine what users concerned with internal organ

diseases, joint pain, fever, school reform, or the military success map receive or experience daily. The so-called artificial intelligence, i.e., algorithms that select information tags to the taste of the reader/listener/viewer, will not just narrow down or limit access to a panorama of more extensive and more significant information other than rheumatoid arthritis or fever. By the way, as regards a bunch of completely thieving officials, note that it is always ex- or former- never the incumbent or today's officials in full power and responsibility. I may admit that one inadvertently looked at an advertising scene of dubious taste. But what is the effect on his/her life?

Any wonder then that our population, having been going in two different directions for several years, is becoming stunned and at the same time aggressive, turning away from the ethical and economic values of international cooperation and Western countries? What was intended as entertaining and useful, a helpful offer of topics "according to your interests", designed to become a navigator in the ocean of primarily digital information, has revealed its reverse side. Generative AI has proven its effectiveness in many areas. However, the algorithm of the corresponding programs do not always help. Experience implanted in the consciousness of the masses with the help of "filter bubbles" has soft-drawing consequences for the public, who do not suspect anything bad; they are unknowingly being drawn into the "funnels" of interests. This problem has become not just technical, technological or psychological but also philosophical.

METHOD

For practical purposes, it is important to go beyond the format of gnoseology to include ethics and social philosophy. Various methods will be employed to encapsulate user interests by selecting requests for information in social networks and highlighting the main topics. Logical methods: analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, "ascent from the concrete to the abstract"; psychological insight; case-study as well as the dialectical way of considering the positive and negative sides of one phenomenon, will feature.

It has to be mentioned that this philosophical essay is built around a special issue of the Springer journal, No. 37, published in the summer of 2023, devoted to the problems of artificial intelligence. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13347-024-00768-2> Two authors of particular interest are: the Italian philosopher Ermelinda Rodilosso, (Rome, Universita degli Studi di Roma Tor Vergata) [1], and the Russian philosopher Artur Karimov (Kazan, Innopolis) [2].

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

I believe that the consequences of the latest technological revolution should be analysed according to the requirements of the dialectical method: 1) in development; 2) comprehensively (at least from two opposite sides); 3) remembering the concreteness of truth and 4) applying the practical determinant of “the connection of the subject with what a person needs”. Note that this revolution is subject to the law of the transition of quantitative changes into qualitative ones: the more users, the higher the “digital tsunami”, and the more radical the social changes. Social network users [and there are now almost five billion of them (of us)] are a very serious audience, in terms of the difficulty of analysis. Something general can still be stated from the very beginning: according to the review Digital 2024 Overview [3], at least a third of netizens pinpoint “reading news stories” as the primary reason why they use social media platforms for long periods. [2, § 2]. A relatively smaller proportion uses artificial intelligence assistance for professional purposes. A convincing example of indispensable help to a scientist is the recognition of the high status of electronic journals; I will name only those with which I closely cooperate: “Journal of Frontier Studies” and “Galactica Media: Journal of Media Studies”. Both were included in the Russian and International databases in the shortest possible time.

Staying in virtual reality, i.e., computer games and VR-controllers that augment reality, can be dialectically assessed as both positive and negative, often even simultaneously. Examples that deserve an unconditional positive assessment are successful training runs and flights carried out virtually (For example, the film “Gran Turismo”, USA, Japan: 2023; the VPC Shadow’s Trophy Tournament competitions on simulator helicopters [4], and many others), and then objectively real.

On the other hand, it is enough to recall the blatant failure of the Unified State Exam system in contemporary Russia, which brought down the Soviet education system and ushered in, according to the assessments of almost all teachers, illiterate school graduates to universities; these are victims of silent computer tests conducted instead of live conversations and commented essays. This also applies to higher degree students.

Another striking example is that at the International Kant Congress held in Königsberg (Kaliningrad) at the end of April 2024, the High Economics School Rector, delivering a welcoming speech at the Opening Session, said that he allows his students to use ChatGPT, which, “by changing the way they work, helps to search and structure information”. This does not mean that HSE

graduates are not scrupulously questioned during the defence of their final qualification work on the subject of mastery of their own and GPT's intellectual product. But the example is indicative. And the Antiplagiat-VUZ system published the following data on July 23 of 2024: every fifth work of Russian students has traces of AI.

It would be too easy today to simply remark that there is a light side and a dark side to digital technology. [5] Discussions about the ubiquitous cyborgs that the future predicts for us often fall into an apology for the “light” and a critique of the “shadow” of trans-humanism and post-humanism, respectively; but perhaps the present day is more important. Returning to our immediate topic, the “Shadow” has already loomed.

If there is a filtration bubble that introduces the user into a state of intellectual (gnoseological) solitude, then it causes or has already caused or will cause – a more formidable loneliness of psychological, ideological, and worldview magnitude. Everyday life cannot be compared with the virtual reality (VR) universe; the latter provides an unrivalled experience, “offering impressive visual effects that surpass reality.” [6]. As a result, the user quickly develops video addiction and a feeling of inferiority, an incompleteness of one’s own existence.

It seems that educational Internet technologies hinder socialization just like home schooling, although there are also optimistic views on this matter. [7]. Possible epistemic isolation could lead to political radicalization, writes Ermelinda Rodillo. “...The enormous amount of data we can access is strictly filtered according to our interests and inclinations. It follows that our experience in social media can be so repetitive and self-validating that it promotes the development of epistemic bubbles: we do not have access to all the relevant data we need, but only to the data that adhere to our interests. Anything that does not collimate with those interests is cut off”. [1].

Constantly but almost imperceptibly experiencing the impact of specially selected information in the web, users can accordingly change or reformulate their beliefs and feel “alarm and daze”, which can lead (at least some of them) to extremism and radical actions. It is enough to remember that the “orange” and “pink” revolutions were organized precisely in social networks.

The “hypersensitive” user, in essence, is just as harmful to a liberal state as an “anesthetized” user, described in Rodilosso’s paper. Both are artificially detached (informationally and emotionally) from the real problems of our society due to being locked in their personal filter bubbles.” [2, п. 2].

Bias and subjectivity of assessment have existed for a long time; they have always existed. If we can still talk about the plasticity of the mind of a child or teenager, then a formed adult always stubbornly defends his/her established convictions and at first welcomes the help of a computer, which confirms his/her views every day. However, now the algorithm created by AI, designed to “focus the binoculars” of a given user on the most relevant information (for him/her), filters out everything that it does not consider to meet the needs of its user, from its field of vision.

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An antinomy arises. On the Internet, you are surrounded by many interlocutors, interviewers and experts, you receive a huge amount of information, etc. That is, sitting in a comfortable chair at home, you seem to be maximally socialized. But “the selective management of Big Data through specific algorithms gives rise to a paradox: we are both extremely connected with and disconnected from the Web. We constantly interact with the kind of information that is consistent with our habitual behaviour on the Web, with little (if any) chance of experiencing unexpected information and data. In other words, we are not guaranteed to be exposed to perspectives other than our own ...” [1].

Psychologists emphasize: “While you are wearing a headset, you do not see the people who are nearby, and they may find it strange that you are nearby but do not notice them. This is a new level of ignoring loved ones.” [8]. And deep dependence on the virtual world gives rise to a feeling of worthlessness. [6].

Therefore, "...it is not superfluous to think about how, after walking through spectacular virtual landscapes, you will have to return... to harsh reality." [9].

Philosophy has lagged somewhat behind psychology in explaining the explosive spread of digital technology: for 'Minerva's owl flies at night'. "The problem inherent in this technological acceleration is that, since it is progressing very rapidly, we don't have sufficient speculative tools to examine it: simply put, philosophy has not been able to keep up with such a pace". [1]. However, it now reveals deeper, more significant manifestations of this latest technological revolution.

E. Rodilosso devotes her article not only to the negative aspects of being locked in a "filter bubble," but to the politically dangerous consequences of this self-isolation. If we do not have sufficient information about the political environment in which we live, our decisions can be biased and polarized, she points out. Being "locked in an epistemic micro-universe" is fraught with ambiguous consequences in the political sphere. Indeed: "The users become so fixed in one strong negative emotion that it makes them oblivious and indifferent to other important issues in our society, thus preventing any rational and critical dialogue with them. Since the latter is a necessary component of a democracy, then a rising number of these individuals would constitute a serious threat to the functioning of a democratic state". [2, § 3. Conclusion].

Not only social networks, but official radio and television act in exactly the same way, relentlessly forming, say, the "image of the enemy"; but these media are intrusive, their pressure is easily felt; while the obliging information provided by the Network is so unlike coercion! Even if it powerfully supported your one-act interest in military actions or threats of natural and social cataclysms by selecting precisely these news items... you still don't believe it is oppression...

Here we will dwell a little longer not on the political consequences of this isolation, but on the following negative phenomena caused by the natural intelligence of the programmer (for AI is a metaphor), and in fact not necessarily exceeding the level of the platform user: 1) loneliness; 2) the illusory nature of virtual reality; 3) suppression of critical thinking.

Loneliness, if it is not a penitentiary punishment, starts as a personally chosen solitude: it can be a rest from labours (righteous or unrighteous), monastic tonsure, poetic soaring, the concentration of a scientist or professional, more or less forced, but still voluntary service to a task. An illustration can be a literary

hero: for example, one of the best Russian writers, Pelevin's S.N.U.F.F. Later, the eclogue of solitude quickly develops into loneliness. Without invoking literary heavyweights like Orwell, we can recall the success of prominent Russian intellectuals such as Pelevin and Vodolazkin. These heroes were well acquainted with both the power of the system and the tragedy of inescapable loneliness. The many-headed (and many-armed) faceless machine intellect will enhance de-realization, offering something more than your life Dasein. But the deadliest shadow of this shadow – the filter bubble capsule – is the loss of critical thinking.

“...If we do not have sufficient information about the political environment in which we live, our decisions can be biased and polarized”. [1]. Every philosopher's treasure trove of critical thinking will not only fail to spread to a wider audience than the academic, but it will not develop at all; the user might not even notice the manipulation. The formation of “filter bubbles” is based on the selection process carried out by “deeply educated” AI programs that “infer” the expectations and value judgments of users, instantly hand-picking the appropriate content. So why study?

CONCLUSION

As Ermelinda Rodilosso rightly wrote, “We can therefore say that artificial intelligence constitutes a promising field that is spreading to many areas of human life - and, perhaps, a new phase of technological revolution” – pays tribute to the success of the “digital”. However, despite all the enormous advantages that programs called artificial intelligence bring, their use optimizes logistics and medicine. They have been adopted by the State Services, education, business, and military. In public publics they are first and foremost invincible weapons, and leaders of influence. The same Rodilosso emphasizes that “artificial intelligence in social networks can actively threaten users' ability to think, compare different positions, and draw independent conclusions. It is becoming increasingly clear that machine learning algorithms permanently used to select content on social networks, hinder the development of critical and pluralistic thinking due to the arbitrary choice of data to which netizens have access. [1].

AI paradoxes have been studied extensively for at least 15 years. Eli Pariser pointed out the problem as far back as 2011. It is quite possible that fears about the power of AI may be exaggerated. Generated texts and pictures, sometimes quite successful, cannot but surprise and even cause an approving reaction. Marketing platforms today cannot do without computer support, this

became especially clear during the Covid-19 pandemic. As for the three vices of “epistemic bubbles” that give rise to ethical and other social problems, the following must be said:

Loneliness which leads to frustration. However, there are many psychological techniques that help cope with this negative state. 2) The virtual reality paradox which is simply resolved: perform as much live communication, walks, travel as possible, “find five pluses in each of your days,” etc. 3) Much more serious and dangerous is the loss of the ability to think independently. This is the conclusion not only of philosophers but also of psychologists and neuroscientists. As Levina puts it, “We become unable to carry out serious cognitive processes... to think strategically, to invent something new, to reflect and to work on mistakes... and when we cannot think, we are also unable to think about ourselves – there is no identification.” [10].

In short, the loss of critical thinking is the loss of thinking altogether. A weak mind receives information without absorbing it for long, and it is unable to set personal goals and chart the trajectory of its bearer’s life. Such a scenario would lead to “a world of disparate individuals living in an illusory universe.” [10]. As a philosopher, I think there is a way out: and these are squarely the philosophical sciences: epistemology, logic, ethics, philosophical anthropology, as well as artistic classics. It is precisely about reading books and personally writing essays without the help of GPS. In addition, netizens should critically assess situations, and not just watch videos. As a personal opinion, I would suggest introducing a compulsory special course in higher education: a detailed study of the sayings and letters of Epicurus that have survived to our time and are beautifully commented on. Although, of course, there could be contemporary names: let it be Harman, Meillassoux, Zizek, or Harare. Science is 2500 years old, and an interest in this wealth is guaranteed to hopefully nurture critical thinking.

NB/ Written exclusively from virtual sources.

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